
NEURAL NETWORK PARAMETER SYNCHRONIZATION USING DISTRIBUTED SOURCE CODING PRINCIPLES

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ABSTRACT

Neural networks have helped solve numerous problems and create applications in various fields in the past few years. In order for the neural networks to perform well, the number of parameters has had to grow considerably in size. One problem that this introduces is when one fine-tunes the parameters, a large amount of bandwidth is needed to synchronize other users to use the same parameters. In this paper, we propose a synchronization protocol that uses Distributed Source Coding principles to significantly reduce the bandwidth needed to synchronize these parameters. The protocol incorporates a tree-based quantizer in conjunction with CRC codes. We further demonstrate how LT codes can be used to save bandwidth when a sender broadcasts the parameters to many users.

1 Introduction

In the past decade, neural networks have made tremendous strides in various fields, from multimedia processing to disease prediction [1] to Natural Language Processing [2]. To achieve the improvements, neural networks have had to grow in size and computation. For example, early on Deep Convolutional Neural Networks required on the order of 10 megabytes to 100 megabytes of parameters. Later, Transformer Networks [3] were able to achieve better results and spur new applications, but often required gigabytes to terabytes of parameters. As an example, ChatGPT-4 [4] requires around 2 trillion parameters, and DNABert2 [1] requires around 100 million parameters. Storage and transmission of these parameters are non-trivial. Exacerbating the problem, each network may constantly be fine-tuned or quantized to improve results and computation and the resulting parameters may also need to be stored/transmitted. In this paper, we examine the problem of reducing storage/transmission costs after Neural Networks are fine-tuned/quantized.

We propose a method in which Distributed Source Coding [5, 6] principles may be used to synchronize many different fine-tuned/quantized networks to a single network. Such a scenario arises when for example a network is fine-tuned/quantized to achieve superior results and many receivers wish to update their existing network to the superior network. A naive method would be to send the full parameters to each receiver, incurring potentially gigabytes or terabytes of transmission bandwidth to each receiver. Alternatively, one may think to send a delta of the superior network and each receiver network. Unfortunately, the sender does not know the parameters of each receiver and cannot calculate a delta. This is where Distributed Source Coding Principles are useful for allowing each receiver to “correct” their parameters to the superior set of parameters. The contributions of this paper are:

- Propose a block-based protocol that incorporates a tree-based quantizer in conjunction with CRC codes [7] to synchronize the parameters between a sender and a receiver while significantly reducing the transmission bandwidth.
- Investigate optimizations to block lengths in the proposed protocol.
- Demonstrate how LT codes [8] can be used to save bandwidth when a sender broadcasts the parameters to many users.

Figure 1: Illustration of how a quantization function, $q_1(x)$, can be partitioned into a tree of quantization functions such that the range of $q_1(x)$ is equal to the union of the range of $q_{2^l}(x), \dots, q_{2^{l+1}-1}(x)$ at level l and the ranges of $q_{2^l}(x), \dots, q_{2^{l+1}-1}(x)$ are mutually exclusive

We start by providing relevant background information, followed by our proposed method and concluding with simulations and results.

2 Background

Our work relies on the use of Distributed Source Coding principles. Distributed Source Coding refers to a problem where an encoder attempts to compress a source x , given that there is side information $y = x + z$ that is correlated to the source and available at the decoder but unknown to the encoder. For this problem, compression bounds are well known [5, 6]. Furthermore, there exist code constructions [9] that attempt to achieve these bounds. One practical issue that exists, however, is that the correlation (i.e. z) is often unknown, thus leading to difficulties in making use of existing work.

3 Method

The problem that we are trying to solve is when a user has a fine-tuned set of parameters for a network and would like to share this set of parameters with at least one other user. The naive method is to send the whole set of parameters, but this can become costly when the network is large and/or there are a lot of users. Instead, if the receiving user already has a set of parameters that are correlated to the sending user's parameters then we propose a method that will use much fewer bits by taking advantage of the correlation. Specifically, assume that the sending user has a set of parameters represented by the vector $\vec{w} = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n]^T$ and the receiving user has a set of parameters represented by the vector $\vec{v} = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n]^T$ and \vec{w} and \vec{v} are related by a random vector \vec{z} :

$$\vec{v} = \vec{w} + \vec{z} \quad (1)$$

In the Distributed Source Coding literature [9], it is proposed that error correction codes can be used to convey the correlation between \vec{v} and \vec{w} . Unfortunately, the statistics of \vec{z} are unknown, which makes it difficult to choose a proper error correction code. As an alternative, we propose to partition a quantization function into a tree of quantization functions and have the sender adaptively convey to the receiver the quantization function to use. Furthermore, we assume that the receiver can communicate back to the sender when a set

of parameters is successfully decoded so that overhead is minimized. In the following sections, we shall describe the details of our method.

3.1 Tree-based Quantization

It is assumed that the sender has used a quantization function $q_1(x)$ to generate each of the w_i in \vec{w} . This function is represented by a uniform scalar quantizer in Figure 1 where $q_1(w_i) = \left\lfloor \frac{2w_i + \Delta}{2\Delta} \right\rfloor \cdot \Delta$. We use Δ to represent the quantization interval such that all values within a quantization interval will quantize to a value that is equal to the center of the interval. Note that the range of the quantization function is discrete and represented by the set of values $C_1 = \{\dots, -3\Delta, -2\Delta, -\Delta, 0, \Delta, 2\Delta, 3\Delta, \dots\}$. We refer to C_1 as the set of codewords generated by $q_1(w_i)$. This quantization function can be partitioned into a tree of quantization functions such that the union of codewords generated by each of the quantization functions at a given level is equal to C_1 , and the codewords that are output from each quantization function are also mutually exclusive. Specifically, at level 1 there will be two quantization functions $q_2(w_i)$ and $q_3(w_i)$ that result in codewords $C_2 = \{\dots, -2\Delta, 0, 2\Delta, \dots\}$ and $C_3 = \{\dots, -3\Delta, -\Delta, \Delta, 3\Delta, \dots\}$ respectively. Note that $C_1 = C_2 \cup C_3$. At level l , there will be 2^l quantization functions $q_{2^l}(w_i), \dots, q_{2^{l+1}-1}(w_i)$ that result in codewords $C_{2^l} = \{\dots, -2^l\Delta, 0, 2^l\Delta, \dots\}, \dots, C_{2^{l+1}-1} = \{\dots, -\Delta, (2^l - 1)\Delta, \dots\}$ such that $C_1 = C_{2^l} \cup C_{2^l+1} \cup \dots \cup C_{2^{l+1}-1}$. Thus, for any given level l in the tree, the same codeword can be obtained by using $q_k(w_i)$ where

$$k = \left(\frac{q_1(w_i)}{\Delta} \text{ mod } 2^l \right) + 2^l \quad (2)$$

If the receiver uses $q_k(v_i)$ to quantize each v_i in \vec{v} , then it will be able to recover \vec{w} as long as each $|z_i| < 2^{l-1}\Delta$ for every z_i in \vec{z} . The bits sent by the sender is the bit representation of u_i where u_i is defined as:

$$u_i = \frac{q_1(w_i)}{\Delta} \text{ mod } 2^l \quad (3)$$

and l represents the level in the tree. There shall be a u_i sent for each w_i in \vec{w} . The receiver will then use the following functions to decode its parameters to try and recover the sender's parameters. Each function at level l can be written as a translation of $q_{2^l}(w_i)$:

$$q_{2^l}(w_i) = 2^l \Delta \left\lfloor \frac{w_i + 2^{l-1}\Delta}{2^l \Delta} \right\rfloor \quad (4)$$

$$q_{2^l+u_i}(w_i) = q_{2^l}(w_i - u_i\Delta) + u_i\Delta \quad (5)$$

The receiver can then use $q_{2^l}(v_i - u_i\Delta)$ to quantize v_i to recover w_i .

In the above, we assume that a level l is predetermined in order to recover each w_i from v_i . In actuality, the sender does not know how far each v_i is from w_i (i.e. $|z_i|$), and therefore does not know the level l to use in (3). As a result, we propose to use the above methodology with the following heuristics:

1. Divide \vec{w} and \vec{v} into g blocks (i.e. $\vec{w}_1, \dots, \vec{w}_g$ and $\vec{v}_1, \dots, \vec{v}_g$)
2. Calculate a Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) [7] for each block \vec{w}_j
3. Iteratively send bits starting at level 1 for each level until the receiver is able to decode a block \vec{v}_j that has a matching CRC to the sender's CRC

To determine the number of blocks needed, one should take into account 1) error detection capability of the CRC, 2) structure of the neural network, and 3) redundancy of the CRC. Smaller block sizes will result in more overhead from the CRCs. A mathematical cost function can be found, where x is the number of bits used for the CRC, k is the total number of parameters, $|z_{max,p}|$ is the maximum absolute delta between v_i and w_i in a given block p , and s is the block size:

$$c(s) = \frac{xk}{s} + \sum_{p=1}^{\lceil k/s \rceil} \left(\left\lceil \log_2 \left(\left\lfloor \frac{|z_{max,p}|}{\Delta} \right\rfloor \right) \right\rceil \cdot s \right) \quad (6)$$

Figure 2: Proposed file format for storing synchronization information. Each data block contains a single bit to specify if the entire block is zero and another bit to specify whether a significance map should be stored for the block. This is then followed by the level bits which allow for the decoding of correlated parameters.

To simplify, we can approximate the summation as $k \cdot E[b(s)]$, where $b(s)$ is the bit-width (i.e. $\lceil \log_2(|\frac{z_{max,p}}{\Delta}|) \rceil$) to encode each weight in a block of length s :

$$c(s) = \frac{xk}{s} + k \cdot E[b(s)] \quad (7)$$

To find the minimum of the cost function, we take the derivative of both sides and set it equal to zero, which simplifies to the following:

$$\frac{x}{s^2} = \frac{d}{ds} E[b(s)] \quad (8)$$

The solution to the above would give us the optimal block size (i.e. s). We expect the probability distribution of $|z_{max,p}|$ to be exponential. If we assume an exponential distribution in (8) and solve for s numerically, then we get a value around 119 for a 32-bit CRC and 275 for a 64-bit CRC. The derivation for optimal block size is provided in the Appendix.

In practice, we may want the block size to be a nice fraction of the channel/layer sizes for convolutional layers and matrix sizes for transformer layers. Furthermore, a neural network may be fine-tuned with different methods [10, 11, 12] that can lead to the following scenarios:

1. Entire blocks may be removed (i.e. quantized to zero) [11, 12]
2. Many weights within a block may be quantized to zero (i.e. a sparse block)

To account for item 1, we can send one bit at the beginning of each block to tell the receiver if the weights in the block should all be set to zero (i.e. block is removed). To account for item 2, we can send another bit at the start of each block to specify whether a significance bit should be sent for each weight in the block. The weights of value zero can be ignored when applying the rest of our method. We can use the above heuristics along with practical considerations and optimal block size to determine a practical method to divide a set of neural network parameters into blocks.

3.2 File Format and Block-based Protocol

In the previous section, we described a method in which a receiver can recover a set of neural network parameters, \vec{w} , given that the receiver has a set of parameters $\vec{v} = \vec{w} + \vec{z}$. In this section, we formalize how the necessary information can be stored in a file, so that a protocol can be built to send only the necessary information from the file to a receiver in order to recover the parameters. The file format which may be stored on a repository such as Hugging Face, can be organized as follows: 1) Meta-Data followed by 2) Block 1 Data, Block 2 Data, ... Block g Data (see Figure 2). The Meta-Data contains information about how the neural network is organized, the precision of the quantizer, the number of blocks, and the number of weights per block (i.e. s). Each block's worth of data starts with two bits that specify whether the block has any non-zero weights and whether there is a weight significance map to follow. The weight significance map (if present) specifies whether each weight is non-zero. Following the weight significance map are the bits for

Level 1 to Level L , for each of the significant weights. There needs to be enough levels in the file so that \vec{w} may be recovered from $\vec{v} = \mathbf{0}$.

Each receiver may require varying amounts of information from the file. Thus, we need a communication protocol between the sender and receiver, so that the receiver can notify the sender when it has enough information to successfully decode each block. For blocks that are all zero, only a single bit needs to be sent from the sender to receiver. For blocks that are the same between sender and receiver (i.e. $\vec{v}_j = \vec{w}_j$) only the CRC needs to be sent. For all other blocks, a varying number of levels need to be sent for the receiver to recover \vec{w}_j . In general, if there is more correlation between \vec{v}_j and \vec{w}_j , then fewer levels need to be sent. The complete protocol is documented in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Sender/Receiver Protocol

```

1: for  $k = 1$  to  $g$  blocks do
2:   if all weights in block are zero then
3:     sender: send a zero bit
4:     receiver: set all weights in block to zero
5:     break
6:   else
7:     sender: send a one bit
8:     sender: send the CRC for block
9:     if sender CRC == receiver CRC then
10:      break
11:    end if
12:  end if
13:  if sparse block then
14:    send a one bit
15:    for  $j = 1$  to  $s$  weights do
16:      if weight is 0 then
17:        sender: send a zero bit
18:        receiver set corresponding weight to zero
19:      else
20:        sender: send a one bit
21:        receiver: mark corresponding position as significant
22:      end if
23:    end for
24:  else
25:    sender: send a zero bit
26:  end if
27:  level = 1
28:  while sender CRC  $\neq$  receiver CRC do
29:    for  $i = 1$  to  $s$  weights do
30:      sender: send level bits corresponding to  $u_i$  (see (3))
31:      receiver: decode level bits corresponding to  $u_i$  to quantize  $v_i$  (see (4) and (5))
32:    end for
33:    receiver: calculate CRC
34:    level ++
35:  end while
36: end for

```

3.3 Code Optimization

For the protocol documented in Algorithm 1, note that the number of bits sent for the levels of any given block will equal $max_level \cdot s$, where max_level corresponds to the level needed to correct for $max(|z_i|)$. This can be inefficient if many of the parameters in the block can be recovered with a level that is less than max_level . To save bits, one could consider sending only k parity bits of an error correction code [7] (where $k < s$) to correct for d bit errors at a given level. For each of the levels, the sender can send $k < s$ bits and the receiver can calculate its own level bits by quantizing each v_i within a block with $q_1(v_i)$ and then figuring out the level bits from u_i using (3). If d or fewer of the level bits that are calculated from the receiver differ from the level bits calculated by the sender, then the k parity bits can correct for the bit errors between what the sender would have calculated and what the receiver calculated. One problem with this approach is that d is not known for each level and would need to be approximated, resulting in possible errors or degradation.

Figure 3: An example where a sender broadcasts all level 1 bits to 2 receivers. For level 2, parity blocks are broadcast instead, and both receivers only need a single parity block to recover all level 2 bits.

As a result, one may use powerful error correction codes [13] to come up with an approach to save bits, but we caution that this could come at the expense of considerable complexity.

Next, we consider an optimization when a sender is broadcasting to multiple receivers. In this case, we propose that LT codes [8] may be used to reduce the total number of packets sent and simplify the protocol in Algorithm 1. Specifically, we propose the following steps:

- Group m blocks together and process each group according to below until all groups are processed
- **Sender:** starting at a level i , where $i \geq 0$, send parity blocks via LT codes. For all levels before i , send level bits for all blocks
- **Receiver:** starting at level i , where $i \geq 0$, calculate level bits for blocks that have a CRC that matched the sender. For blocks that do not have a CRC that matched the sender, treat these blocks as erasures, and receive parity blocks until all erasures are corrected. For all levels before i , receive level bits for all blocks and decode according to Algorithm 1
- Repeat above steps until CRCs of all blocks are matching

From the above, each receiver will receive and decode as many blocks as it needs to completely recover the parameters. The total amount of blocks sent may be decreased. For example, in Figure 3, we show a case where all blocks for receiver 1 only need 1 level, except for block 2, which needs 2 levels. For receiver 2, all blocks only need 1 level except block 3, which needs 2 levels. In this example, both receiver 1 and receiver 2 can recover all blocks by receiving level 1 bits in addition to a single parity block that is equal to the XOR of the level 2 bits for block 1, block 2, and block 3. Since both receiver 1 and receiver 2 have CRCs that match the sender for 2 of the 3 blocks after receiving level 1 bits, it can successfully calculate the level 2 bits for those blocks and XOR them with the parity block to recover the missing block.

4 Results

We tested our protocol using various models [2, 10, 14] along with their fine-tuned/quantized version.

One experiment was to test the savings per block size for the cases with and without sending a significance map. Figure 4 shows an example of a sparse model that benefits from sending a significance map. As can be seen from the graph, more than 90% savings can be achieved by sending a significance map as opposed to less than 60% savings when not sending a significance map. Note that this may not be true for all models (see Figure 5). The decision to send a significance map is up to the sender and will vary on a per model basis. One thing that can be noticed from the graph (see Figure 4) is that the optimal block size is typically between 100 parameters and 500 parameters. The drop off in savings after this point is typically minimal. As a result, one may choose to use larger block sizes if it aligns better with the neural network structure (e.g. layer/channel sizes, transformer matrix sizes, etc.). Another thing to note is that we chose to use a 32-bit

Figure 4: A graph of bit-rate savings vs. block size for a BERT model

Figure 5: A graph of bit-rate savings vs. block size for a ViT model

CRC in our simulations. This should be sufficient to detect errors with a high probability given smaller block sizes. If one were to choose a much larger block size, then a 64-bit CRC may be necessary.

We also tested our protocol on several different models stored on Hugging Face (see Table 1) to find the optimal block size for each model. In Section 3.1, we found that the optimal block size is typically around 119 from Equation (8) for a 32-bit CRC. While this is true for a couple of the models that we simulated, it was quite a bit off for other models. One reason for this is because we approximated the summation in Equation (6) as $k \cdot E[b(s)]$. In practice, this approximation may not hold. For example, if a block uses a significance map, then not all parameters (i.e. w_i) will need level bits. Furthermore, some blocks may be coded with a single bit (i.e. all zeros) or a single CRC (i.e. sender and receiver blocks are identical). In terms of bit-rate savings, we found the savings to vary between 62% and 99% with an average of 80.4% and a standard deviation of 12% for the models that we tested.

Table 1: Optimal block size and savings over multiple models

Model Type	BERT	LLM	BERT	ViT	BERT	LLM	BERT	BERT	LLM	BERT	Min	Max	Std	Mean
Optimal Block Size	150	100	500	200	500	100	200	500	200	200	100	500	158	265
Savings (%)	85	97	90	87	62	95	66	79	99	74	62	99	12	80.4
Weight Significance Bit	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	-

Finally, we tested the use of LT codes for the case where the sender broadcasts to several receivers. In general, we found that LT codes are more beneficial when there are more receivers. Also, the results may vary significantly depending upon the heterogeneity of the correlation between the different receivers and the sender. More investigation is needed in this area to characterize the savings versus varying differences in the correlation distributions between receivers.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we explored the problem of synchronizing parameters between a sender and receiver(s). We proposed a protocol based on Distributed Source Coding principles that significantly reduces transmission bandwidth (e.g. up to 99% in some cases). We also examined how block sizes can be optimized in our protocol and proposed how LT codes may be used in broadcast scenarios to further reduce bandwidth. For future work we would like to do more investigation on LT codes and their constructions.

6 Acknowledgement

I would like to dedicate this paper to my grandma, Hua Chou, who has always been one of my biggest supporters but passed away on March 30, 2025.

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Appendix

A Distribution of z_i

In order to find the optimal block size, we need to determine the distribution of $|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}|$. For all of the models we looked at, the distribution of $|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}|$ aligns closely to an exponential distribution. Figure 6 shows the graph of the distribution for z_i , for one of the models we downloaded from Hugging Face.

B Block Length Optimization

To find the optimal block length, we need to find $E[b(s)]$. We start by assuming that $|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}|$ is exponentially distributed (see Appendix A). To find $E[b(s)]$, we need to find $E[Y]$, where

$$Y = \max\left(\left|\frac{z_1}{\Delta}\right|, \left|\frac{z_2}{\Delta}\right|, \dots, \left|\frac{z_s}{\Delta}\right|\right) \quad (9)$$

and

$$E[Y] = \int_0^{\infty} P\{Y > y\} dy \quad (10)$$

Note that $P\{Y > y\} = 1 - P\{Y \leq y\}$ and

$$P\{Y \leq y\} = P\left\{\left|\frac{z_1}{\Delta}\right| \leq y\right\} \cdot P\left\{\left|\frac{z_2}{\Delta}\right| \leq y\right\} \cdot \dots \cdot P\left\{\left|\frac{z_s}{\Delta}\right| \leq y\right\} \quad (11)$$

where we assume that each $|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}|$ is independent and identically distributed. For each $|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}|$, we have

$$P\left\{\left|\frac{z_i}{\Delta}\right| \leq y\right\} = (1 - e^{-\lambda y}) \quad (12)$$

Equation (11) then becomes

$$P\{Y \leq y\} = (1 - e^{-\lambda y})^s \quad (13)$$

so that

$$E[Y] = \int_0^{\infty} 1 - (1 - e^{-\lambda y})^s dy = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{k=1}^s \frac{1}{k} \quad (14)$$

Figure 6: An example distribution of z_i for a BERT model

where $\sum_{k=1}^s \frac{1}{k}$ is the Harmonic sum and can be approximated as $\ln(s) + \gamma$, for large s and $\gamma \approx 0.577$. From the above

$$E[b(s)] = \lceil \log_2 E[Y] \rceil \approx \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} (\ln s + \gamma) \right) \quad (15)$$

Applying this to our cost function, we get

$$c(s) \approx \frac{xk}{s} + k \cdot \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} (\ln s + \gamma) \right) \quad (16)$$

We can take the derivative of $c(s)$ to get

$$\frac{d}{ds} c(s) \approx -\frac{xk}{s^2} + \frac{k}{(\ln s + \gamma) \ln 2} \cdot \frac{1}{s} \quad (17)$$

To minimize $c(s)$, we set the derivative equal to 0 and simplify

$$s = x \ln 2 (\ln s + \gamma) \quad (18)$$

We cannot solve equation (18) analytically, so we wrote a program to solve for (18) numerically using Newton's method. For a 32-bit CRC, we found the optimal s to be approximately 119, and for a 64-bit CRC, we found the optimal s to be approximately 275.